

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NICKSON****FIRST NAME: TABAN****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 5-7 key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Introduction to Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6 -12)
2. Writing Good Academy Essay (EUCLID 2024, 15)
3. Avoiding Plagiarism in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 34 -39)
4. Using American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 25 - 32)
5. Essay styles and guides (EUCLID 2024, 40 - 56)
6. Using Latin abbreviations and expressions in Essays (EUCLID 2024, 58 - 62)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

The start of this journey came with excitement and apprehension as I embarked on this new chapter of my academic and professional growth. It took me months to decide and enroll for this course, which I finally made on March 15, 2024, and effected registration in the LMS portal on April 1, 2024. Upon my first login, I was confused about where to start, but I had to familiarize myself with EUCLID University protocols and what I am supposed to do by reading through the provided instructions and watching the video provided; this gave me a clue in writing this response paper.

As a student who originated from where English is used as a medium of instruction from my pre-primary to my master level, I thought my English was perfect. However, through this course, I realized there is a lot that I need to learn, unlearn, and relearn to comprehend my English. Furthermore, the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D period one (1) document revised by Prof. Lauenet Cleenewerck and Dr. Karibu Gulma provided me with further knowledge on citation styles, paragraphing, punctuations, spellings, and

putting headings. In addition to the above, I further gained skills in writing essays, avoiding plagiarism, and distinguishing between American and British language styles.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMY ESSAY

This chapter on the ACA-401/ACA-401D period one-course pack provides skills in essay writing, outlining the steps required to prepare before writing any essay. To write a comprehensive essay, the paper indicated that planning is a vital tool for the best essay writers. This plan should outline and hint at what you will write in your essay's introduction, body, and conclusion. In writing an academic essay, answering the question by providing relevant evidence and concluding with your analysis is essential as it enriches the information you provide on the topic. I agree with this concept of essay writing because it enables one to systematically plan one's work and align to the respective sections and notes taken during your sketching time. I further agree that taking notes on key issues makes us avoid plagiarism, as notes are only made for critical points, and expounding those points makes one think broadly and provide relevant experiences (EUCLID 2024, 11).

3) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM IN ESSAY WRITINGS

Plagiarism is a core area when it comes to essay writing; according to EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D period one-course pack (EUCLID 2024, 33), plagiarism is the use of sources of information without giving credit to the author of any idea that writer borrows to enrich their work. This has been a significant concern in the academic arena. As a result, most institutions have embarked on ensuring students' work is thoroughly checked using various software. Therefore, this course pack has broadened my skills in ensuring that I consider all the articles and writings ethically by citing all the sources of information I include in my paper.

4) USING AMERICAN & BRITISH ENGLISH

Globally, two types of English are commonly used. Although both are world English, most British colonized countries mostly use British English. However, recently, there has been a growing dominance of some countries using American English, mainly attributed to the steady growth in international significance coupled with the high population since World War II (EUCLID 2024, 25), whereas many people still use a mixture of the two types. Although there is no difference in pronunciation, some spellings use the same terms and words. As a result, this course pack provided approaches to using a specific type.

Therefore, having reviewed the literature of the two versions in English, it should be noted that using a mixture of both British and American can easily change the meaning depending on the reader. The course pack indicates that the two versions cannot be used interchangeably; hence, one must decide which version to use.

5) ESSAY WRITING STYLES AND GUIDES

Essay writing must be well formatted in a particular style to make the document look organized. Therefore, styling is a means of documenting your approach to some aspects of writing style that must be consistent (EUCLID 2024, 41).

This course pack clearly gave me knowledge through this styling guide, which spells out the basic rules in writing that will allow consistency. From this course, it is essential to know that styling is necessary for particular institutions. For example, ECLUID provides a clear guide of the style they require in writing their response paper; similarly, all publications, journals, and articles have their required style. Therefore, this chapter of the EUCLID course pack one is vital because it gave me the guide to handling styling regarding my professional journey at ECLUID University.

6) USING LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS IN ESSAYS

An abbreviation is a shortened form of a word or phrase by any method consisting of a group of letters or words taken from the full version of the word. EUCLID University provided skills on when and where to use it. For example, before this course pack, I did not know Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes and biographies. However, the course pack recommends using equivalent English words to avoid misinterpretations (EUCLID 2024, 59), I agree with this because to communicate clearly to your audience, ensure you communicate in simple terms to attract the reader's attention.

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D period one-course pack of the EUCLID University has provided a stepping stone towards my professional journey in pursuing my Ph.D. in Monitoring, Measurements, and Evaluation. I gained a lot from the various chapters of the component, such as English, using Latin abbreviations, writing an essay, styling my documents, and watching the video, which added more flavor.

Furthermore, the course pack reminds us that learning and unlearning are continuous processes we should always embark on in our professional journey. It further gave me the courage to believe that by the end of the course, my knowledge will be enriched in my monitoring, measurement, and evaluation profession and a vast general academic knowledge.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.